

EXTENSION OF REFORMATSKY REACTION. PART I. STUDY WITH ETHYL BROMOMALONATE AND ACETONE.

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Reformatsky reaction with ethyl bromomalonate and acetone follows an unexpected course. One molecule of the former reacts with two molecules of the latter leading to the formation of ethyl acetonylisopropylmalonate which has been characterised by its cyclisation to 5:5-dimethyldihydroresorcin and hydrolysis to a dilactone. The mechanism of the reaction is explained.

The classical Reformatsky reaction for the synthesis of β -hydroxy-esters consists in the condensation of the α -bromo-ester of a monocarboxylic acid with a ketone in the presence of zinc. Studies with various ketones and oxides, and α -chloro-, bromo- or iodo- esters of monocarboxylic acids are reported in literature (Lawrence, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 457; Clemo and Ormston, *ibid.*, 1933, 362; Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 582; Nieuwland and Daly, *ibid.*, 1931, 53, 1842; Fuson and Farlow, *ibid.*, 1934, 56, 1593; Myers and Lindwall, *ibid.*, 1938, 60, 644; Fuson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1938, 60, 2272; Arbusow, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 1430). Having failed to see any mention of a Reformatsky's synthesis using the α -halogen ester of a dibasic acid, it was thought to be of interest to study the reaction of ethyl bromomalonate with acetone in the presence of zinc. (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1935, p. 146). Under the normal course the β -hydroxy-ester (I) would be expected.

But the reaction takes a different course leading to the formation of acetonylisopropylmalonate (II) (b. p. 135-137°/4 mm.) from two molecules of acetone and one molecule of ethyl bromomalonate. The structure of (II) was proved by its cyclisation to 5:5-dimethyldihydroresorcin (III) (semicarbazone, m.p. 74-75°; Vorlander and Erig, *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 314) on treatment with sodium methylate and subsequent hydrolysis with alkali. On hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid the ester (II) gives the dilactone (IV) (m.p. 135-36°). Qudrat-i-Khuda (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 201) prepared (II), which he named as ethyl ester of α -carboxy- γ -acetyl- $\beta\beta$ -dimethylbutyric acid and the dilactone (IV) by the condensation of mesityl oxide with cyanoacetamide. The alkali hydrolysis of 6-hydroxy-2-keto-3-cyano-4:4:6-trimethylpiperidine (V) gave the acid (VI) which

was esterified to (II) and subsequently cyclised to (III). When the piperidine derivative (V) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid the dilactone (IV) was formed. The melting points of the products (IV) and the semicarbazone showed no depression when admixed with the respective ones prepared according to Qudrat-i-Khuda.

In all the experiments excess of acetone (3 molecules to one of bromoester) was used. Suspecting that the excess of the ketone was misdirecting the normal Reformatsky reaction, in a trial experiment only molecular proportions were used. However, the product isolated was the same (II); only a quantity of zinc and ethyl bromomalonate were recovered unreacted, thus indicating the need for excess of acetone. Further from the low boiling fractions of the reaction mixture, mesityl oxide was isolated. Therefore, it becomes necessary to assume that due to the influence of zinc and ethyl bromomalonate, formation of mesityl oxide takes place in the system. Kohler, Heritage and Macleod (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, **46**, 217) have studied the action of methyl bromomalonate on benzalacetophenone in presence

of zinc, where due to 1:4-addition at the conjugated system, methyl- γ -benzoyl- β -phenylethylmalonate (VII) is formed as under

They have established that with bromomalonic esters and unsaturated ketones only 1:4-addition happens under these conditions. In analogy to this, the mechanism of the present reaction is explained as follows. Two molecules of acetone condense to give mesityl oxide. Later the zinc compound of ethyl bromomalonate adds on to it in 1:4-position leading to the formation of (II) as below.

Apparently this is not a true Reformatsky reaction although molecular proportion of zinc is consumed. The possibility of the formation of the hydroxy-ester (I) in the early stages of the reaction and its subsequent condensation with another molecule of acetone to form (II) is ruled out as there is neither any indication during the present investigation nor any mention of a parallel case in literature. Incidentally, experiments using diacetone alcohol and mesityl oxide instead of acetone, also yield only (II).

It is hoped to extend the work with other ketones and halogen esters of dibasic acids.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl bromomalonate was prepared by brominating malonic ester in carbon tetrachloride (Organic Synthesis, 1927, VII, 34).

Ethyl Acetonylisopropylmalonate (II).—To ethyl bromomalonate (47.8 g.) and dry acetone (34.8 g.) taken in a 500 c.c. round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser and guard tube, and heated on a water-bath purified zinc wool (14 g.) was added in small quantities. Very often the reaction commenced immediately; on occasions it had to be started by the addition of a trace of iodine. After the entire zinc was added it was refluxed for about 2 hours and the excess of acetone distilled off. Water was then added and the resulting mixture was treated with dilute sulphuric acid. The separated oil was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution was successively washed with dilute sulphuric acid and water, and finally dried with magnesium sulphate. The residual oil (23 g.) from ether was distilled at $170-175^{\circ}/34-36$ mm., or at $135-37^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 9 g. (Found: C, 60.31; H, 8.53. M. W., 256.9. $C_{13}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 60.47; H, 8.53 per cent. M. W., 258).

Cyclisation of (II) *to* 5:5-Dimethyldihydroresorcin (III).—Ethyl acetonylisopropylmalonate (12 g.) was cyclised by refluxing it for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours with anhydrous methyl alcohol (50 c.c.) in which sodium (1.5 g.) was dissolved. The mixture was again refluxed for another 5 hours after the addition of caustic potash solution (8 g. in 100 c.c. of water). Alcohol was then removed and the product isolated after acidification with hydrochloric acid, m.p. $146-48^{\circ}$ (mixed m.p. with a genuine sample), yield 3 g.

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. $74-75^{\circ}$ (mixed m.p. with Qudrat-i-Khuda's preparation), yield 3 g. (Found: N, 13.06. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{26}O_5N_3$: N, 13.33 per cent).

Hydrolysis of (II) *and Formation of the Dilactone* (IV).—The ester (II, 5 g.) was refluxed with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1, 40 c.c.) till the oily layer disappeared. It was then filtered and evaporated to dryness. The pasty mass was purified by successive treatment with acetone and benzene and the solid crystallised from water, m.p. $135-36^{\circ}$, yield 1 g. (mixed m.p. with Qudrat-i-Khuda's product). (Found: C, 58.98; H, 6.49. Calc. for $C_9H_{12}O_4$: C, 58.73; H, 6.52 per cent).

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